

A heuristic for fitting piecewise-linear models of bivariate functions with simplices and its application to an industrial use case

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Figure: The current paths toward the iron and steelmaking industry. Source: <https://www.cesaref.eu/>

Empty ladle stage

Full ladle stage

- Scheduling model (empty stages)
 - Continuous time formulation
 - Deterministic parameters
 - Minimize waiting and heating times
 - Constrained by refractory temperature
 - P1: unrelated parallel machine scheduling
 - P2: flow-shop scheduling
 - P3: non-linear energy balance
- Complex MINLP problem
 - Convert to MILP with piecewise linear models
 - Leverage exact solvers
 - Optimality guarantees

Figure: The different decisions involved in the ladle dispatching problem

Piecewise linear models (PWL)

Requires a J1 compatible triangulation (Vielma et al., 2011)

Figure: Example of J1 triangulation considering a lifetime of 0 for the **heating operation**. A simplex is highlighted in red with black stripes. We used eight breakpoints per variable.

- Approximation quality directly affects the optimal solution
 - Increase the number of breakpoints
 - Reduces the error...
 - but the problem quickly becomes intractable
- How to obtain good approximations with the minimum number of triangles?

Figure: Approximation error of the linearized model (Ruela et al, 2023).

□ Univariate functions:

- Heuristics (Camponogara et al., 2015)
- Exact and heuristic methods (Rebennack and Kallrath, 2015)

□ Multivariate functions:

- Partition with convex polytopes (Toriello et al., 2012), (Duguet et al., 2022), (Kazda and Li, 2021), (Kazda and Li, 2023)
- Partition over triangles (Rebennack and Kallrath, 2015)
 - Closest to our work

Much work is available in the efficient representation into MILP, but not for optimally fitting PWL models

- Focus of our work
 - Find error-bounded PWL approximations for continuous and smooth bivariate functions
 - Triangulation generated over a rectangular grid
 - Compatible with the LOG representation (Vielma et al., 2011)
- Objectives
 - Fit J1 compatible triangulations
 - Respect a given error tolerance
 - Fewer linear pieces
 - Easy-to-implement
- A simple method to construct adequate PWL models
 - We do not expect it to provide the best PWL approximation!
- Source code available:

<https://gitlab.tuwien.ac.at/iet/public/pwl-heuristic-CESAREF>

$D, b_{max}, n_{1,0}, n_{2,0}, \delta^{max}$

Initialization $t = 1, \delta_0 = \infty$

Rectangular grid fitting

$b_{1,t}, b_{2,t}, \delta_t$

Grid size adjustment

$n_{1,t}, n_{2,t}$

No $\delta_t \geq \delta^{max}$

TC?

Yes $n_{1,t}, n_{2,t} \leq b_{max}$

$t = t + 1$

- On each iteration
 - Solve NLP to adjust the placement of the linear pieces to minimize the approximation error

$$\min_{\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2} \max\{|f(\mathbf{x}_i) - y_i| : \forall i \in [1, \dots, m]\}$$

$$s.t. \quad \mathbf{b}_{d,1} = \mathbf{b}_d^{\min}, \forall d \in [1, 2]$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{d,n_d} = \mathbf{b}_d^{\max}, \forall d \in [1, 2]$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{d,j} \geq \mathbf{b}_{d,j-1} + \epsilon, \forall d \in [1, 2], \forall j \in [2, \dots, n_d]$$

$$f \in S(\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2)$$

- $\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2 \rightarrow$ J1 triangulation
- Solve a (non-convex) constrained NLP to minimize the maximum absolute error
 - Can be easily modified to use different error metrics

- On each iteration
 - Solve NLP to adjust the placement of the linear pieces to minimize the approximation error
 - Then increase the number of breakpoints for the variable with maximum error reduction potential.

PWL fitting heuristic

No significant error difference?

↓

Increase both

- Benchmark functions used in (Rebennack et al., 2015) and (Kazda et al., 2021).
- Experimental setup
 - D : 30 evenly spaced breakpoints
 - Constrained solvers from *scipy*:
 - DE and SQP
 - TC: 1000 iterations + default
- Working as expected
 - But cannot approximate well the most complex functions
- DE outperforms SQP in regards to the number of linear pieces
 - SQP can suffer from local convergence
- However, the time required can be considerably higher!

Figure: J1 triangulation and predictions from the PWL models fitted for the benchmark functions using the different evolution (DE) solver.

Application - Ladle scheduling problem

Legend: Parameter Decision variable

- Heuristic applied to the refractory temperature model
 - D : 30 evenly spaced breakpoints
 - DE solver
 - Baseline: 12 evenly spaced breakpoints (Ruela et al., 2023)
- The proposed heuristic needs significant time for strict error targets
 - Limited application if domain bounds are changed often

	Baseline			Target-Baseline			Target-10				
Stage	n_1	n_2	δ	n_1	n_2	δ	Time (s)	n_1	n_2	δ	Time (s)
Empty	12	12	17.23	4	6	15.01	3608	5	7	9.94	11029
Heating	12	12	54.52	6	4	35.62	3143	6	8	8.21	19937
Casting	12	12	14.06	7	7	11.93	20409	7	8	9.73	32162
Full	12	12	39.41	7	5	23.11	7387	5	10	9.85	16900

Table: Comparison of the heuristic results for different error targets.

Figure: The approximation error for configuration Target-10 for each ladle operation

- ❑ Three different instances were evaluated
- ❑ The runtime is significantly reduced
 - Optimality is proven much faster
 - Fewer decision variables
- ❑ **Target-10** achieved the best balance between solution time and approximation error
- ❑ Small deviations observed in the optimal objective

Scenario	Configuration	BV	CV	δ	Time (s)	Objective
1	Baseline	2509	18347	32.72	10000	1440
	Target-Baseline	2215	6209	29.04	967	1431
	Target-10	2236	7448	17.96	1205	1421
2	Baseline	4096	22268	23.4	2026	947
	Target-Baseline	3760	8396	25.3	716	949
	Target-10	3784	9812	13.07	525	940
3	Baseline	3235	22089	26.49	2416	1567
	Target-Baseline	2885	7639	22.88	1278	1568
	Target-10	2910	9114	22.93	1417	1560

Table: Computational results of heuristic applied to the ladle dispatching problem

Time: ↓ 67%
Error: ↓ 34 %

- ❑ Heuristic to compute PWL approximations for a J1 triangulation for continuous and smooth functions
- ❑ Applied to a complex industrial use case
 - Accurate approximations with fewer variables
 - Significant performance improvements
- ❑ Some directions for improvement were identified
 - Compare our method with existing ones when applied to the ladle scheduling problem
 - Reduce runtime
 - Explore the application of different exact solvers
 - Evaluate different approaches for the grid size adjustment heuristic

How to fit J1 compatible triangulations for more than two dimensions?

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Learn more

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